

Effect of Manpower Training and Development on Employee Performance

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to examine the effect of manpower training and development on staff performance in Federal College of Education, Zaria. The survey research design method was used in this study which involves using a self-design questionnaire in collecting and using data from two hundred and forty eight (248) employees of the college. Linear regression analysis was used to analyze the data with the aid of Social Statistical Package for social sciences (SPSS) version 22. The results revealed that the independent variables: manpower training, manpower development have significant strong positive influence on employees' performance. It is therefore recommended that Training and development of employees should be seen as prerequisite by the management of college of education and every other business organization and the contents should be well be planned in line with organizational objectives and that regular training should be done intermittently.

Keywords: Employee Performance, Manpower Training, Manpower Development, Organisational Success, Development Programmes

1 INTRODUCTION

Teacher's education has in the last few decades received attention in Nigeria. Such cognizance is not unconnected with the recognition by the Nigerian education planners that no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers. In order to produce quality and professionally qualified teachers for the Nigerian educational system, the Nigerian National Policy on Education (1998:3rd edition) holds that Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) as the minimum entry qualification into the teaching profession. Institutions designated to provide the required professional training for teachers at various levels is Colleges of Education, Faculties of Education, Institutes of Education, National Teachers Institute and Schools of Education in the Polytechnics.

It is therefore clear that the effectiveness and success of an organization depends on the people who form and work within the organization. It follows therefore that the employees in an organization to be able to perform their duties and make meaningful contributions to the success of the organizational goals and needs must acquire the relevant skills and knowledge (Kulkarni, 2013). So, in order to achieve the aforementioned organizational success manpower training and development is seen as the ultimate mechanism for organizational success, though traditionally before manpower training and development programmes are organized, efforts must be put in place through individuals and organizational appraisals to identify the training needs. After the training and development programme, an evaluation is carried out to ascertain the effectiveness of the programme in line with the needs earlier identified. It is believed that organization development follows the development of individual who form the organization (Mustapha, 2019). In view of that no organization becomes effective and efficient until

the individuals have applied the required skills and knowledge suitable for carrying out their responsibilities without hindrance. It is right to say that both administrators and academicians cannot be successful without well trained and competent personnel. However, the need for organization to embark on staff development programme for employees has become apparent and absence of these programme often resulted into problems of incompetence, inefficiency and ineffectiveness (Kulkarni, 2013). Manpower training and development aim at developing competences such as technical, human, conceptual and managerial for the furtherance of individual and organization growth. Nevertheless, the process of manpower training and development is continuous, since it is sociologically agreed that man is dynamic in nature, the need to be current and relevant in all spheres of human endeavor makes employees development a necessity, to keep track with current events and methods. The globalization phenomena and organization dynamism coupled with technological proliferations and dramatic changes in management strategies, structures, and government ideology and policy have constituted grave global concerns amongst employers, academics and organizational experts cannot be disputed and equally affected employees working skills, attributes, expertise and performance as well as organization continuity, sustainability, growth, development and possibly decay (Sule, 2021).

Over time, organizations have been embarking on training and capacity building for their employees so as to enhance productivity and overall performance of the organizations. This is due to the recognition of the important role of training and manpower development in attainment of organizational goals (Malaolu & Emenike, 2013). Training has been an important variable in increasing organizational productivity. Colombo and Stanca (2008) showed that training is a fundamental and effectual instrument in successful accomplishment of the firm's goals and objectives, resulting in higher productivity. They added that training and manpower development build a team that is effective, efficient and well motivating, thereby enhancing the confidence and self-esteem of employees. All over the world, training has been seen as a core function in private sector organizations and central to the public sector, whose employees need to be trained to face the new challenges and pressures for innovation created by the current atmosphere of increased globalization. It is obvious that the act aims to upgrade employees' knowledge and raise the level of their performance which is turned into better service delivery and public assets management in public sector.

However, the inconsistency in the existing empirical evidence was reported and this makes it imperative to provide further empirical evidence on the effect of training and manpower development on employee productivity. In addition, despite the effort of empowering employees with skills through training and development practices, the achievement of government and public sector goals have been subject of criticism in terms of poor service delivery, lack of motivation, poor public assets management and lack of influence on the minds of the employees in terms of achieving organizational goals.

That is, there should be a clear link between investment in human capacity building and organizational performance. The study, therefore, aims at investigating the impact of manpower training and development practices on employees' performance of FCE Zaria.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Conceptual Issues of Manpower Training and Development

Staff training and development come under the purview of personal function in most organization, whether public or private. The importance of staff training and development in any organization is clear if we recognize the fact that the structure that sustains it depends on the individuals that operates the structure. Staff training and development can occur simultaneously or complementary, but the two do not necessarily have direct relations to each other. Training and development are defined by Obi and Zakari (2017) as any

initiatives to enhance the present or future performance of a worker by improving the capacity of the employee to function by learning, typically through enhancing the skills and knowledge of the worker. Jones, George, and Hill (2000) assume that training concentrates mainly on educating employees of organizations on the way to conduct their jobs and aiding them in gaining the skills and knowledge needed to be successful employees. Training is about acquiring knowledge and skills for work purposes, training is more job-oriented or task-oriented (Jones, George, & Hill, 2000).

Onifade et al. (2020) described manpower development as an economic resource, constituting skills and attitude which is derived from education and training that provides labour with the ability to organize and carryout an economic process when apportioned. The focus of manpower development for improvement is on employees and organizations, in order to enhance their competencies and boost their values so as to positively impact on their productivity (Obi-Anike, Ozioma, Ofobruku&Okafor, 2017).

Mitchell (1979) also noted the popular convention to think of training as dealing primarily with operative personnel and development, with managers and executives. He went on to treat each of the concepts separately. However, he admits that “even though while there are differences between the two processes, there is also considerable overlap” Ngu (1990) opined that it is safer to argue in favor of this “Considerable overlap” because there is very little to be say of their differences. To him (Ngu) “both Training and development are purposefully geared towards improvement on skills and performance. Both involve moulding or removing of workers characteristics towards this end. The differences between the two processes may be in content and method. Training might be offered by various methods including coaching and mentoring, peer cooperation, and subordinate involvement. Such teamwork allows workers to engage effectively in the work and create better results, thereby boosting the performance of the company (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). Ofobruku (2015) asserts that the development of manpower enhances the efficiency of employees which in return would allow the corporation to obtain better overall performance of organizations. To meet business objectives, expenditure in human capital is required to ensure that employees possess the necessary proficiency and expertise to function effectively in a dynamic and complex climate.

Ngu (1990) defines training and development as “The process of behavioral modification or molding of workers in order to integrate organizational needs with their characteristics. Manpower training is viewed as a means of equipping employees with the necessary skills and knowledge to enable them perform their job better and as a way of solving employee problem of self-improvement, advancement and better placement. Training involves formal and informal methods and both could be on or off the job training.

The efficient of any organization depends directly on how well its members are trained. Newly hired employees usually need some training before they take up their work: Older employees require training to keep alert to demands on their present Jobs and to prepare for transfer, and promotion. Training also motivates employees to work harder. Employees who understand their Jobs are likely to have morals, they are able to see a closer relationship between their effort and performance. Effective managers recognize training as an ongoing continuous process not a one-short activity; new problems, new procedures and equipment, new knowledge and new Jobs are constantly creating the need for employee instruction.

Training and development is so important that it is not only imperative but continuous. No organization can dispense with it as a programme and as a process. Supporting this view, Pigor and Myers (1980) admit that “no organization can choose whether or not train employees.” All new employees, regardless of previous training, education, and experience need to be introduced to their new employer’s work environment and to be taught how to perform specific tasks.

Training may be defined as an organized and coordinated development of knowledge skills and attitudes needed by an individual to master a given situation or perform a certain task within an organizational setting. Craig (1967) defines training as the development process made possible through the device of words and signs. So training is the formal procedures which an organization uses to facilitate employees learning of the organizations as well as the individual's goal and objectives.

Staff development on the other hand, according to Akpan (1982), is the process whereby an employee is enabled to grow in the job, through the acquisition of work experience, breadth and increasing confidence resulting from the exercise of varied and tested responsibilities. The aim is to enable him to reach the top or achieve his best in his profession of employment. Such a position will be attained through action, observation, study reflection, experiment and initiative (Onah, 2003). As Cole (2002) puts it staff development should be seen as any learning activity which is directed towards further needs rather than present needs and which is concerned more with career growth than immediate performance. The focus of staff development tends to be on the organization's future staff requirement and on the growth needs of individual in the work place.

2.1.1 Manpower Training and Development Objectives, Needs and Content

Training is a process that develops and improves skills related to performance. Training objectives or needs can be derived from the manpower situation. The existing manpower situation determines the training objectives both as organizational and national level. To be able to identify training needs, therefore, will entail a comprehensive manpower survey which is usually an aspect of manpower planning (Ngu 1990:27)

Caldwell identify four major training objectives, this includes the achievement of capable men and women prepared through training to perform the tasks that the national welfare requires, mobilizing for attach upon national problems thirdly a tool for enlarging human resources and productivity, fourthly, the designing for constructive channeling of human resources. These training objectives as identified by Caldwell are rather two broad with emphasis on national training policies and objectives with no emphases on organization. The objectives of manpower training and development can be summarized thus:

- i. Improve efficiency, and morale
- ii. Introduce new techniques
- iii. Provide for succession, enables qualified replacement to be available
- iv. Raise the standard of unskilled personnel, thus helping overcome Labour shortage.
- v. Develop supervisors and decrease the amount of supervision needed.

It is pertinent to note that most organization does not regard training as professional activities, and in many cases training officers are not themselves trained. Many courses are held and employees sent on courses or educating unskilled though without any serious though being given to the real training needs of an organization.

Effective training Programme, according to Blun and Naylor (1976), can result in increased productivity, reduces Labour turnover and greater employee satisfaction. They should include all employees from factory, workers to executives and apply not only to inexperience workers but also to experienced workers new to the enterprises. They also note that a training Programme should also include those that are promoted to higher level jobs and the periodic retraining of present employees by means of refresher course.

In this direction, MC Cornick and Tiffin (1977) categorizes training programmes in organizations into three forms, namely orientation training, on-the-job-training, off-the-job training. Closely related to the above,

are the training needs of the staff in organization. MC Cornick and Tiffin believe that training needs differ from group. According to them, the training needs of people in organizations tend to fall into two groups which more or less blend into each other. First, there is the need to provide specific Job training, especially, for new employees and sometimes for present employees who are deficient in job performance. Second, there is the need in most organizations to provide training of a personnel development nature that will contribute to the longer –range effectiveness of the individuals' question. Although personnel development training programmes have generally been limited to executives and the managements class, the changing times emphasis the desirability, of such training for other groups in order to combat the occupational obsolescence of professional and scientific personnel.

Tobias (1967) view the following as a balanced manpower programme; Recruitment, Development, motivation, Education, training, utilization and stabilization. To him, training programmes prepare the worker for efficient Labour force participation with respect to giving occupation. He concludes that training is endless so long as a man works, he learns and teaches others at all levels regarding management development, Ubeku (1975) observes that the plan of management development should aim at;

- i. Systematically transferring general management knowledge, policies and procedures for managing the company to all managers.
- ii. Appraising and maintaining all inventory of all candidates moved as qualified for replacements for manager positions.
- iii. improving the present performance of all managers' on-the-job development methods directed at individual needs
- iv. Broadening managers for higher responsibilities through outside and on-the-job programmes activities and courses.

In general, Nigro and Nigro (1977) feel that the objective of an executive development programme is to improve the executive and understanding of such areas as planning, coordination, communication, decision-making, delegation, headquarters, field relations, legislative relations, and public relations.

Writing on the training and development of the executives in developing countries, Mutahaba (1986) opines, that it is no longer in dispute that training and development of public administrators contribute to improve performance. This increasing acceptance of the importance and significance of training in public administration is according to Stone and Stone (1978) and Goshin (1979), indicated by the attention giving to it in many countries of the world.

Ubeku (1975) notes that employees who have not received adequate training before being assigned responsibilities lack the necessary confidence with which to carry out their jobs. He then suggested that an employee should be helped to grow into more responsibility by systematic training and development so that he will be confidence enough to carry out the responsibility of the job. This, according to him, is because training increases the employee's belief that he knows what is expected of him regarding the job, the knowledge of which enables him to originated ideas as to how best to carry out this task of the job. Conversely, those not trained tend to cling to methods they were shown the first time they took over the job and are frightened at doing the job in a different way because something might go wrong and they cannot afford to take the risk.

It was observed that even-duo, there is a training policy in the institution right from its inception, and its implementation has been half hardly pursued. Due to the nearness of University of Abuja, to the school, some staff has succeeded in arguably some form of training without depending on the institution for anything. Many staff of the institution proceeds to studies without the prior knowledge and approval of the

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institution, As such, they are not under a bond and can therefore leave the institution for other jobs opportunities after the training program. Due to this deficient in the training policy, the institution has continued to witness high Labour turnover among the academic and the non - academic staff, these problems might not be tackled unless manpower training and development is given a sizeable attention by the institution.

Hilgert and Dowl (1978) in their book lifted cases and policies in Human Resources management” look at the training and development of staff as not only capable of reducing organizational/employee conflict but can also motivate staff in their work place. In their own words, a well-conceived training and development program can contribute to a lessening or reconciliation of conflict. Thus, a challenge and an opportunity is presented to even manager to make each employee better able to serve the firm, while at the sometime realizing greater satisfaction of individual needs and aspiration.

Furthermore, the authors observations that training is also related to employee motivation agrees with French’s (1978) notion that employees who knows and understand their Jobs and who feel that for future management values they are enough to prepare them for assignments are more likely to demonstrate higher morale and greater interest in the Job.

French (1988) describes the dynamism of motivating people through training programme in the following words:

“In order to change behavior in the direction of greater contribution to the attainment of organizational goals, the individual must perceive the new expected behavior serving to fulfill needs at least, and not leading to deprivation of fulfillment. Supplementing goals and needs that are within reasonable reach of employees is very important in providing motivation as it relates to training and development. In other words, the environment must be conducive to change in behavior”.

The implication of the training motivation correlation for organizations sponsoring their employees on training programmes-is perhaps more critical for the public service, particularly in developing countries where government is the largest employer of Labour and the problems of motivating the workforce is rather daunting. The task of the public services as an organization seeking to improve the performance of its workforce through training is to guarantee an environment conducive for the trainee to return to or else beneficiaries of employee –sponsored training programmes would not see training received as a motivator for greater job performance. The point is all the more important given, the facts that the need for an organization training its employees in the first place is to equip them with knowledge that would enable them to contributes their quota to organizational growth and development. Since the final learning in whatever sphere of organizational activities takes place on the job, it is crucial that all external training is planned to help the trainees or employee meet the on-the job demands. Thus, as soon as possible after the acquisition of the necessary or new knowledge, the employee should have the opportunity to put the acquired knowledge to practical use. In the words of French, to be effective, training and development must be perceived as leading the attainment of need satisfying goals as well as to the avoidance of ego-damaging events”

Gibson (1972) has given an elaborate definition of the desired goals sought by training as productivity maintenance and productivity enhancement. In terms of productivity maintenance, he further asserted that, and I quote:

“Much of human resource training is a form of maintenance expense. New people are constantly being lured and must be indoctrinated and trained. Experience productive employees leave the company for many

reasons, such as retirement and are replaced by those who need training and experience. In term of productivity enhancement, he opined that some training and development may be, or can be strategic in nature, that is designed to obtain fuller utilization of human resources and thereby increase rather than merely maintaining productivity.

In his process system model of organization, French viewed the training and development functions of organizations as a process which is a complex amalgamation of many sub-processes aimed at increasing the capability of individuals to contribute to organizational goal attainments.

Thus, so far, all the literature review point of anything that's is the importance of manpower training and development to an organization cannot be over looked or jeopardized

The last area of the concepts of manpower training and development to be discussed is training needs.

Training needs are basically any short fall in employee performance or potential performance which can be remedy by appropriate training (Cole, 2002). There are many ways of overcoming deficiencies in human performance at work, and training is only one of them. It is important to recognize this fact, since sometimes trainee staff are asked to meet needs which ought to be dealt with in some other ways, such as improving or replacing machinery or simplifying procedures.

As lack of training is dysfunction to organizational performance, adequate care should be taken to recognize when training is needed. According to Nwachukwu (1988: 121) occasions that employees in any organization require training include the following ; lack of interests in one's job negative attitude to work, low productivity, Tardiness, excessive absenteeism rate, excessive complaints, highly rejects or low quality output, high incidence of accidents and insubordination. Whenever these conditions are experience among staff, Nwachukwu contends that the organization should consider organizing training. As those situations are frequent occurrences in organizations, the implication is that training has to be regular. Put precisely, training should be a continuous exercise in every well-run establishment. Every time you get someone to do work the way you want it done, you are training, every time you give instructions or discuss a procedure, you are training. It is along this principle that's the Civil Services Reform in Nigeria emphasizes that training of Civil Servants will no longer be sporadic, unstructured and anomic. It stated further that training would henceforth be considered as a right of every civil servant and an obligation on the government.

Once the symptomatic indicators of training needs here been observed the most next important things to do is to determine which area training is needed. This step is important becomes training could be a waste of time and resources if the area of emphasis in training is not precisely isolated (Beach 1975; 375), (Nwachukwu, 1988: 123).

Therefore, the need for training has to be identified specifically before embarking on any training programmes. According to Beach (1975) a rational way of identifying the area of training need is to analyze the entire organization (people, Job, technology etc). Thus, troubled spots where training may help could be identified. The analysis involves the following practical steps.

- i. Identify organizational and production problems i.e. low productivity, high cost, poor material control, poor quality and excessive scrap and waste, excessive Labour management strife, excessive grievance, excessive violation of rules of conduct and poor discipline, high employee turnover, excessive absenteeism, and delayed production.
- ii. Analyze Jobs and employees: Job analysis, employee appraisal and testing.

- iii. Collect employee and managerial opinions through interviews and questionnaires to obtain views regarding perceived problem areas and deficiencies which would indicate desirable training programmes.
- iv. Anticipate impending and future problems and expansion of business, new products, new services, new designs, and new plants.

Now technology, organizational changes, staff inventory compare present staff resources with forecast needs.

2.2 Hypotheses

In order for reliability and accuracy of this work, the Researcher would like to put forth the following:

Ho₁: Manpower training has no significant positive effect on employee performance.

Ho₂: Employee development has no positive effect on employee performance

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This study is based on human capital theory proposed by Schultz in 1961 and developed by Becker in 1994. According to the theory, Human capital theory suggests that education or training raises the productivity of workers by imparting useful knowledge and skills, hence raising workers' future income by increasing their lifetime earnings (Becker, 1994).

The human capital model suggests that an individual's decision to invest in training is based upon an examination of the net present value of the costs and benefits of such an investment. Individuals are assumed to invest in training during an initial period and receive returns to the investment in subsequent periods. In his view, human capital is similar to "physical means of production", e.g., factories and machines: one can invest in human capital (via education, training, medical treatment) and one's outputs depend partly on the rate of return on the human capital one owns. Thus, human capital is a means of production, into which additional investment yields additional output. Human capital is substitutable, but not transferable like land, labour, or fixed capital.

Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2008) in their studies titled 'Human Capital Theory: Implications for Educational Development' focused on the benefits of human capital to the nation as a whole. They pointed out the relationship between education and economic growth. According to Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2008) 'Many of the classical economists argued strongly for government's active support of education on the grounds of the positive externalities that society would gain from a more educated labour force and populace. While formal education has expanded rapidly in many countries, a large portion of human capital accumulation in the forms of on-the-job training and other modes for working adults actually take place both inside and outside the workplace (Jin, 2001).

Theoretical Framework Figure 1, shows the model of this research study; in which Training and development are the independent variables, whereas, employees Performance is the dependent variable.

Fig. 1 Model of the Research Study

This study will continue basing on the above mentioned framework specially it has been mentioned effect of the motivation and manpower Training and Development on staff performance.

Independent variable of the study is training and development while the dependent variable is staff performance. Employee performance consisted of three dimensions namely; employee productivity, employee absenteeism and job satisfaction.

Employee Productivity: Productivity is achieving cost effective high performance and good performance brings quality, higher quality of employee services implies lower costs and increased their productivity, which in turn provides the firm with a greater market share and enhanced competitiveness levels.

Employee Absenteeism: Voluntary non-attendance at work, without valid reason. Absenteeism means either habitual evasion of work, or willful absence as in a strike action. It does not include involuntary or occasional absence due to valid causes, or reasons beyond one's control, such as accidents or sickness.

Job Satisfaction: Employee satisfaction is the terminology used to describe whether employees are happy and contented and fulfilling their desires and needs at work. Many measures purport that employee satisfaction is a factor in employee motivation, employee goal achievement, and positive employee morale in the workplace.

3 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey research design. The population used for this study consists of academic staff of FCT College of Education, Zaria. According to the information made available by the Establishment Unit of the College, as at 2023, there are five (5) Schools/Faculties with a total of 248 staff. , These five Schools and their respective population are: Arts and Social Sciences (47), Education (52), Languages (45), Sciences (61) and Vocational and Technical Education (43). Due to the fact that the population is not much, the entire population will be employed, hence a census population is employed. Taking into cognizance the nature and objective of the study, the researcher used primary source of data collection. Under the primary source of data structured questionnaire will be used. The technique for Data collection was using both quantitative and qualitative methods using excel and Statistical Packages for Social Sciences.

4 ANALYSIS

Table 4.1 Summary Item Statistics of Staff Performance

	Grand Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Means	2.432	2.175	2.876	.701	1.322	.072	5

The result of data analysis presented in Table 4.8 showed that all 4 out of 5 items had their Mean less than 2.5 which is the bench mark mean. The only statement that the mean is greater than 2.5 says that employees of College of Education hardly absent from work and recorded a mean score of 2.8759. The grand mean of 2.432 implies that the performance of employees of College of education, Zaria is below the cut-off mark which can be described as not satisfactory enough.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: H01 There is no significant effect between training and employee performance.

Table 4.2: Model Summary of Effect of Training and Employees' Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.926 ^a	.857	.856	.29054	0.455.

a. Predictors: (Constant), ManPower Training

b. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance

Analysis in table 4.2 shows that the coefficient of determination between the variables are very strong at R=0.926. This is an indication that the relationship between the variables i.e. manpower training and staff performance is very strong. The percentage variation in the dependent variable being explained by the changes in the independent variables i.e. R square equals 0.857, that is, manpower training explains 85.7% change in staff performance. While 14.3% are variations which are unexplained by the independent variable.

Table 4.3: ANOVA of Effect of Training and Employees' Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	68.543	1	68.543	812.015	.000 ^b
	Residual	11.396	135	.084		
	Total	79.939	136			

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Manpower Training

ANOVA findings (P- value of 0.00) in table 4.3 show that there is correlation between the independent variables (manpower training and development) and dependent variable (Staff performance). An F ratio is calculated which represents the variance between the groups, divided by the variance within the groups. A large F ratio (812.01), indicates that there is more variability between the groups (caused by the independent variable) than there is within each group. Referred to as the error term and also show that the model fit the data. The P value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 of the significance level.

Table 4.4 Coefficients of Effect of Training and Employees' Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.317	.078		4.046	.000
	Manpower Training	.818	.029	.926	28.496	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employees Performance

Table 4.4 shows the regression output indicating the strength of value of $\beta = 0.818$ which is the level of effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

The data findings from the table 4.14 above shows that taking at training being taken at zero, a unit change in training will lead to a 0.818 change in employee performance, at 5% level of significance.

Hypothesis Two: H02 There is no significant effect between employee development and employee performance

Table 4.5: Model Summary of Manpower Development and Employees' Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.876 ^a	.767	.765	.37155	.397

a. Predictors: (Constant), manpower development

b. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance

Analysis in table 4.5 indicates the effect of manpower development on employees' performance. The coefficient of determination between the variables are very strong at $R=0.876$. This is an indication that there is a strong relationship manpower development and staff performance is very strong. The percentage variation in the dependent variable being explained by the changes in the independent variables i.e. R square equals 0.767, that is, manpower development explains 76.7% change in employees' performance. While 24.3% are variations which are unexplained by the independent variable

Table 4.6: ANOVA of Manpower Development and Employees' Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	61.302	1	61.302	444.051	.000 ^b
	Residual	18.637	135	.138		
	Total	79.939	136			

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), manpower development

The ANOVA statistics show how well the independent variable fit the dependent variable The F-statistic that measures the how adequate and fit the model is being used in the study is estimated as 444.051 with a p-value of 0.000 which is significant at 5%; this shows that the model is fit for the data.

Table 4.7: Coefficients of Manpower Development and Employees' Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-1.726	.200			-8.636	.000
	Manpower development	1.301	.062	.876		21.073	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance

The table 4.7 indicates the regression coefficient output having a Beta value which is the value of Y that implies that means value of dependent variable, that is organizational performance when there is one unit change in independent variables. The value of $\beta = 1.301$ show that manpower development has a strong effect on employees' performance

5 DISCUSSION

The outcome of the tested hypotheses showed that manpower training and development has significant effect on employees' performance. This is in tandem with the findings of Obikeze, Obi and Abonyi, (2005) who maintained that the primary benefits of manpower training and development are organisational growth, increase employee motivation, increase employee morale, job satisfaction and so on. On this ground the need for training and development of manpower in organisation arises.

The findings is also similar to the outcome of Abiodun (2021), who found out that manpower development is paramount to organizational efficiency. This may be so give that through training, individual employee becomes more proficient in their responsibilities, change their attitudes and beliefs to be in tune with that of the organization and strife diligently to meet the organizational goal.

The result of this study supports is in agreement with the findings of Onifade etal. (2020) which sees manpower development as key to employees' efficiency. In same vein, the study supports Obi-Anike et al (2017) who posited that manpower development leads to higher level of effectiveness. The findings of this study is also line with the findings of Subraanian, Shamsudin and Ibrahim (2011) that manpower planning and development could influence organizational performance because employees skills, knowledge and abilities can be enhanced and be up to date.

6 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

From this study it is obviously proven that institutional performance depends greatly on manpower training and development because trained and developed Staff will be able to translate their improved human capital into improved institutional performance. Manpower training and development is a program designed intentionally for the workers of an organization, to let them work towards delivering the organization to it desired destination. These are the destinations that a company has set for themselves in order to achieve success. On-the-job training and off-the-job training methods are required by the staff in order to achieve these objectives through effective methods of training and development of manpower.

In view of the primacy and indispensability of the role of manpower training and development in accomplishing organizational goals, corporate organizations should set up regular training and development programs that are capable of boosting the skills, morale and productivity of employees. It is extremely recommended that business and organization people managers consult with specialists when determining their organization's training and development requirements.

As a result, there will be less wastage, both in terms of time and resources, because employees will only be provided with what is genuinely required and extremely relevant to their demands. When this is done, the objectives of personnel training and development will be realized, therefore place the organizations at a level of greater performance.

Based on the findings and the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. There is need to identify the training needs of an individual to ensure that the right training is given to an individual employees of college of education and this training should be intermittent.
- ii. Training and development of Staff should be seen as prerequisite by the management of college of education and every other business organization and the contents should be well be planned in line with organizational objectives.

7 LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

Similar studies can be conducted out by other researchers to examine the effects of motivation training and development on staff performance in other tertiary institution in Nigeria, especially Polytechnic and University. The current study was conducted on academic and non-academic staff that are not a management staff of college of education, Zaria, however, there is opportunity to study the effect of training on other senior staff of the college or any other institution of learning or any reputable organization.

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this paper titled 'Effect of Manpower Training and Development on Employee Performance' is a product of my research work, the data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request and there is also no conflict of interest.

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